

Interview questions

Part 1 - General information of the interviewee

- What is the role that you are currently taking?
- Would you like to describe general things you and your team are working on?
 - Follow-up question if not mentioning autonomous driving: is there anything related to autonomous driving systems in your work?
- Have you been involved in any part of the testing in your work?
 - If yes, what testing activities/approaches have you been using?
 - If not, any observations you could share with us on testing, for example, how and who is performing the test?

Part 2 - How critical scenarios are identified and used for testing?

- As there are various scenarios to be considered in testing, some research studies focus on identifying critical scenarios, and others focus on covering different types of scenarios. It will be exciting to hear your opinion on how different approaches can be used or complement each other.
- What do you think of using critical scenarios for testing autonomous driving systems, do you consider it a relevant approach for testing the AD systems or any limitations have you seen?
 - If yes, can you describe how the approach is used, for example, any tools, processes, insights, or observations you might share?
 - If not, any limitations you see that have hindered its use in practice?
- The research studies have shown very effective results in generating critical scenarios but may be irrelevant, e.g., suiciding scenarios. How do you think the test scenarios we generate could be more realistic and relevant?
 - If yes, how could the test scenarios be evaluated and validated?
 - If not, what do you think should be improved for critical scenarios?
- Among the approaches from academic research studies, e.g., expert knowledge, search-based, or data-driven, do you find any of them would be interesting/useful to explore further?
 - If yes, how could these approaches be used?
 - If not, are there any limitations that hindered them from being used?
 - How to improve the industry relevance of academic research? Are you getting anything useful from academic research?

Part 3 - General or other questions

- Are there any open challenges you would like to discuss for testing autonomous driving systems?
- Would you like to recommend any other interviewees on this topic?